

Research Article

**Study on Uterine Scar Dehiscence in in cases having
Previous C-Section during trial of labour**

**¹Aqsa Khalid, ²Faran Tahir
and ³Hassan Nawaz**

¹Women Medical Officer, THQ Hospital, Sadiqabad,
Cell: 03002007444, Email: aqsakhalidrai@gmail.com

²Medical Officer, RHC Manthar, Rahim Yar Khan

³Medical Officer, District Health Authority Bhakkar

ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess uterine scar dehiscence in in cases having previous c-section during trial of labour

Material and methods: This descriptive study was conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, THW Hospital Sadiq Abad from January 2016 to June 2016. Total 100 patients with previous one c-section were selected for this study.

Results: Total 100 patients were selected for this study. Mean age of the patients was 29.55 ± 6.37 years. Mean gestational age was 38.87 ± 2.25 weeks. Scar tenderness was developed in 12 (12%) patients during labour trial. Out of these 12 patients, scar dehiscence was observed in 16.87% patients.

Conclusion: We concluded that the frequency of patients with previous one Cesarean section who develop scar tenderness during trial of labour are not remarkably higher and the trial of labour in these patients may continue confidently and thus decrease rising cesarean section rate in our population.

Keywords: Previous one Cesarean section, trial of labour, scar tenderness, Scar Dehiscence, frequency

INTRODUCTION

There are three possible outcomes for the woman who has had a prior cesarean delivery: a successful trial of labor culminating in vaginal birth, a failed trial of labor after cesarean delivery resulting in a repeat cesarean delivery during labor, or an elective repeat cesarean delivery.

Planning the route of delivery for the woman who has had a previous cesarean delivery should be addressed early in her prenatal care, and can begin preconceptionally. With either approach, women who have undergone a prior cesarean delivery are at risk for serious maternal and perinatal complications and should be counseled about the risk and significance of these complications. (1)

In the USA for instance, Federal Acts and regulations, as well as professional guidelines, clearly demonstrate that every pregnant woman has the right to base her maternity care decisions on accurate, up-to-date, comprehensible information. (2)

The decision for elective repeat cesarean delivery or trial of labor after cesarean delivery with the goal of achieving a vaginal birth should be made by the woman in consultation with her provider. In order to make this decision, both clinicians and patients typically desire individualized information about the chance of successful TOLAC and the balance between the risk of

maternal or fetal morbidity if TOLAC is unsuccessful and the risk of maternal and fetal morbidity with ERCD. (5)

An important consideration while anticipating trial of labour after cesarean section(TOLAC) is the risk of rupture of uterus.¹ In an attempt to decrease the rate of uterine rupture much research is affected to identify the factors that are associated with it³. The incidence of catastrophic rupture, where the maternal and infant lives are in serious jeopardy, is difficult to record, as this event is frequently included with the more common much less troublesome dehiscence. Though, the morbidity of dehiscence is clinically more lower than rupture, prenatal identification of an extremely reedy or a dehisced LUS is belived to be prognostic of subsequent rupture of uterine during the labour⁴. Induction of labour should be avoided, if possible, because it reduces the probability of success and increases the risk of uterine rupture in a trial of labor after cesarean section². The rate of dehiscence of a lower segment transverse uterine scar is 2 to 4% but of a vertical is more higher.⁸

Palpation of abdominal scar to examine the tenderness may provide a clue for probable scar dehiscence although it has not been confirmed in studies.⁹ Females having scar dehiscence complaint of pain and tenderness over the lower segment, various studies demonstrated that scar dehiscence occurs for less frequently what is thought in Lower Segment Cesarean Section⁸.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This cross sectional study was conducted at Department This descriptive study was conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, THW Hospital Sadiq Abad from January 2016 to June 2016.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients with previous one c-section.
- Patients with singleton pregnancy with cephalic presentation(on USG).
- Patients with gestational age 37-41 weeks.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with cephalopelvic disproportion assessed by pelvic examination
- Pregnancy with medical disorder like PIH.
- Known classical / inverted T shaped scar.
- Patients with diabetes mellitus.

Data collection procedure:

Total 100 patients as per inclusion/exclusion criteria were selected. Demographic profile of the patients i.e. name, age, parity was noted. The patients went into spontaneous labour trial of labour was given after excluding any contra-indication. Scar tenderness was a clinical finding that is noted on examination and the intraoperative findings were noted dehiscence present or not. Before performing a repeat cesarean section other parameters like CTG, maternal vital signs were also noted.

All the collected data was entered in SPSS version 17 and analyzed. Mean and SD was calculated for numerical data and frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Total 100 patients were selected for this study. Mean age of the patients was 29.55 ± 6.37 years. Mean gestational age was 38.87 ± 2.25 weeks. Scar tenderness was developed in 12 (12%) patients during labour trial. Out of these 12 patients, scar dehiscence was observed in 16.87% patients.

Findings of present study regarding frequency of scar tenderness during trial of labour and frequency of scar dehiscence among scar tenderness. A study showing that there were a total of 7 cases of complete and partial scar dehiscence(2.6%). Only 3 of 7 cases(42.8%) of scar dehiscence were associated with preoperative scar tenderness.¹⁰

Stone et al studied 89 women with one previous caesarean section reported the rate of vaginal delivery as 66% while 2% had uterine scar dehiscence rate.¹¹ Another study by Del Valle et al in a retrospective series also reveal no major maternal or perinatal complication.¹² Norman and Ekman applied 0.5 mg prostaglandin E2 gel

intracervically and achieved a 63% vaginal delivery rate while no case of uterine rupture.¹³

However, the frequency of scar dehiscence comes out to be negligible or very small in these patients, this is helpful for us to continue confidently trial of labour in patients with previous one cesarean section who develop scar tenderness and thus decrease rising cesarean section rate in our population.

Table 1: Frequency of Scar Tenderness during Trial of Labour (n=100)

Scar tenderness	No. of patients	%
Yes	12	12
No	88	88

Table 2: Frequency of Scar Dehiscence (n=12)

Scar dehiscence	No. of patients	%
Yes	2	16.87
No	10	83.33

CONCLUSION

We concluded that the frequency of patients with previous one Cesarean section who develop scar tenderness during trial of labour are not remarkably higher and the trial of labour in these patients may continue confidently and thus decrease rising cesarean section rate in our population.

REFERENCES

- Madaan M. Trial of labour after previous cesarean section: The predictive factors affecting outcome. *JOG*, 2011;31(3):224-28.
- Caughey AB. Vaginal Birth After Cesarean Delivery 2011 <http://emedicine.medscape.com/article/272187-overview#a30>
- De Beer HJM. Maternal and neonatal outcomes of women who attempted a vaginal birth after Cesarean Section 2009.
- Cheung VYT. Sonographic measurement of the lower uterine segment thickness: I it truly predictive of uterine rupture? *JOGC*, 2008.
- Khan S. Uterine Rupture: A review of 34 causes at Ayub teaching Hospital Abbotabad. <http://ayubmed.edu.pk/JAMC/PAST/15/sameera.htm>.
- Garza P. Spontaneous Uterine Rupture: report of two cases. *Cir* 2012;80:78-82.
- Maureen Boyle. Emergencies around child birth 2nd ed.2011.
- Taj G. Review of study avaginal birth after C-Section (VABC). *Annals* 2008;14(1).
- <https://www.busypr.com/discussion/15/586/bu-syspr-mrcog-part-ii.html>.
- Kausar S. Safety of scar on repeat second C-Section in patients with previous I C- Section. *South Asian Fed of Obstet and Gynecol*, 2009;1(2):26-28.
- Stone JL, Lockwood CJ, Berkowitz G, et al. Use of prostaglandin E2 gel in patients with previous caesarean section. *Am J Perinatol*. 1994;11:309–12.
- Del Valle GO, Adair CD, Sanchez-Ramos L. Cervical ripening in women with previous cesarean deliveries. *International J Gynecol Obstet*. 1994;47:17–21.
- Norman M, Ekman G. Preinductive cervical ripening with prostaglandin E2 in women with one previous cesarean section scar. *Acta Obstetricia Gynecologica Scandinavia*. 1992;71:351–5